

RADx-UP CDCC Leadership and NIH Meeting
October 7th, 2021 at 4pm EST

Rosy Bailey

Project Director - Bridges to Health

puentes@hispanicservicescouncil.org

Engaging Hispanic/Latino/Latinx Working Group: Purpose Statement

This working group will bring together RADx-UP awardees and community partners engaging Hispanic/Latino/Latinx populations. Working group members will have the opportunity to share experiences, challenges, and best practices in COVID-19 communication and outreach, COVID-19 testing and diagnosis, COVID-19 vaccination, and COVID-19 data collection and dissemination with Hispanic/Latino/Latinx populations. The working group will also facilitate shared learning among community, academic, and NIH stakeholders.

Engaging Hispanic/Latino/Latinx Working Group: Goals

- ▶ Goal 1: Advocate for the creation and use of linguistically and culturally appropriate research measures.
- ▶ Goal 2: Discuss best practices for building trust with Hispanic/Latino/Latinx populations.
- ▶ Goal 3: Request and share tools for engaging Hispanic/Latino/Latinx populations.

WHO ARE WE?
26 years serving the
Latino Community in
Florida (Tampa Bay)

Health: Our Approach

Utilize Promotoras who are
trusted members of the
community to educate and
connect their neighbors to
social services and health
and wellness information.

Our Journey with Research & RADX-Up

Projects we participate in:

- ▶ Based on a community need
- ▶ Elevate the voices of our community
- ▶ Build the capacity of our community, agency, or program
- ▶ Have an impact at the policy, system, and environment level
- ▶ Build or expand partnerships
- ▶ Have a high potential for success

Our Journey with Research & RADX-Up

Things we considered for participating in Radx-Up

- ▶ The trust we had developed in the community
- ▶ Previous work assisting the health department with a health impact assessment
- ▶ The resources at hand
- ▶ Experience we had with other research projects
- ▶ Ability to expand our partnership with our academic partner

Radx-Up Project:

Social, Ethical, and Behavioral Implications (SEBI) Research on COVID-19 Testing and Vaccine Uptake among Rural Latino Migrants in Southwest Florida

**Committed to 500 surveys in rural migrant Latino communities
(in addition to focus groups and other interventions)**

Our Journey with Research & RADX-Up

How we adapted the CDE's for the Latino Migrant Community:

- ▶ HSC raised concerns immediately with our academic partner
- ▶ Held focus groups with community members, key informants, and Promotoras
- ▶ Had Spanish speaking staff from the university deliver the survey to our Promotoras
- ▶ When we began executing the survey in the community, we raised issues where we thought the survey was not capturing the voice of the community

Our Journey with Research & RADX-Up

Changes to CDE's & our Approach:

- ▶ Reduce the number of questions
- ▶ Simplify the language of the questions
- ▶ Change the order of questions
- ▶ Train the Promotoras to ask the complicated questions in different ways
- ▶ Add “does not apply” or “prefer not to answer” as options
- ▶ Deliver surveys on a one-to-one basis (Promotora reading the questions)

Our Journey with Research & RADX-Up

Some community feedback/observations:

- ▶ *“This feels like an interrogation.”*
- ▶ Impatience sets in and individual keeps asking, *“Is it almost over?”*
- ▶ Individual starts to “shut down” and begins to answer very quickly in a negative (answers no or does not apply to questions)
- ▶ Interruption from kids/family result in questions having to be repeated frequently (making it take longer)

Our Journey with Research & RADX-Up

Unintended Consequences:

- ▶ Potential for trust to be lost
- ▶ The voice of the community might not be accurately captured
- ▶ Difficult for Promotoras to get participants for future research/future surveys
- ▶ Resources of CBO are stretched further
- ▶ CBO's might not participate in future research

Our Journey with Research & RADX-Up

Positive Aspects:

- ▶ Capturing valuable information about our community
- ▶ Elevating the voice of our community to a national level
- ▶ Connecting with other thought leaders and learning new ways to deliver programs/information
- ▶ Building the capacity of our leadership and our Promotoras
- ▶ Finding our voice and role in research
- ▶ Feel like we are a true partner in research because of inclusion in RADX-Up workgroups and project wide meetings

Questions?

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727-224-8594

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